

COMPARISON OF EFFICACY OF DEXMEDETOMIDINE VERSUS TRAMADOL FOR POST-SPINAL ANAESTHESIA SHIVERING

A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Dear Readers & Researchers,

I am pleased to submit my research synopsis titled "Comparison of Efficacy of Dexmedetomidine Versus Tramadol for Post-Spinal Anaesthesia Shivering." This randomized controlled trial aims to address the ongoing debate regarding the superior drug for managing this common and uncomfortable side effect of spinal anaesthesia.

The study will be conducted at the Department of Anaesthesiology, Bolan Medical College, Quetta, under the supervision of Dr. Amjad Ali. By comparing the efficacy, side effects, and hemodynamic stability of dexmedetomidine and tramadol, we hope to provide valuable evidence to guide clinical practice and improve patient comfort.

Thank you for considering my research synopsis. I am eager to contribute to the field of anesthesiology and look forward to your feedback.

Sincerely,

Dr. Sibgha Saliha

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND:

Anesthesia causes rapid shivering. Shivering can impede wound healing and post-anesthesia discharge by raising intraocular and intracranial pressure. Tramadol helps with post-spinal anaesthesia shivering. The patient may experience nausea, vomiting, dizziness, etc. 2-adrenoceptor agonist dexmedetomidine is a sedative that has also been found to lower shivering.

OBJECTIVE:

- To compare the outcome of dexmedetomidine with tramadol for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering

STUDY DESIGN:

- A randomized controlled trial

STUDY SETTING:

- Department of Anaesthesiology, Bolan Medical College, Quetta.

STUDY DURATION:

- 6 months after approval of synopsis

From: _____ to _____

METHODOLOGY:

Patients aged 18-40, of either gender, who undergo elective surgery under spinal anaesthetic, suffer post-spinal anaesthesia

shivering of grade 1 or greater, and are ASA status I-II were included in the research. Patients were randomized to groups by lottery. Group D received dexmedetomidine 0.5mcg/kg intravenously over 10 minutes. Group T received tramadol 0.5mg/kg intravenously over 10 minutes. The operating room temperature is 24-26 °C. Patients were evaluated for shivering degree, duration, and recurrence (if any). Hypotension, bradycardia, and respiratory depression were also seen.

RESULTS:

The mean age in Group D was 29.8 ± 4.47 and 30.57 ± 4.74 in Group T, 6(17.1%) of Group D and 10(28.6%) of Group T were male, while 29(82.9%) of Group D and 25(71.4%) of Group T were female. Mean shivering duration in Group D was 3.74 ± 1.06 and 4.97 ± 1.22 in Group T, $p=0.0001$. Shivering recurrence was 6.1% in Group D and 25% in Group T.

CONCLUSION:

- We concluded that that dexmedetomidine has greater efficacy as compared to tramadol for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering

KEYWORDS:

- ***Spinal anesthesia, shivering, dexmedetomidine, tramadol, outcome***

INTRODUCTION

Anaesthesia is an essential part of surgical procedures. It can either be regional (including spinal, epidural, etc.) or general anaesthesia. In general, local anaesthesia is cheaper and is presumed to be safer and associated with far less complications related to anaesthesia in comparison to general anaesthesia ^{1, 2}. Spinal anaesthesia can be associated with shivering despite patient being normo-thermic. Mechanism by which shivering occurs in association with spinal anaesthesia is still poorly understood ³. Shivering is defined as a syndrome of involuntary oscillatory contractions of muscles that can occur as a temperature modulation mechanism and also as a side effect of anaesthesia ⁴.

Although shivering is an important physiologic function, it is quite troubling for the patients who have undergone surgical procedure as it leads to increased total body oxygen consumption⁵ (putting prone patients at risk of ischemia), stretching of surgical incision and intensification of post-surgical pain ⁵, which makes management of this much important. Opioid agents like tramadol has been classically used for management of post-spinal anaesthesia shivering and has proven to be effective in reducing the incidence of post-spinal shivering⁶. Similarly,

newer agents like dexmedetomidine, an alpha-2 adrenergic receptor agonist, is also being used effectively for this⁷.

Studies have been done to compare the efficacy of dexmedetomidine versus tramadol for management of post-spinal anaesthesia shivering and have reported controversial results. A recent meta-analysis compared the effect of dexmedetomidine and tramadol on the treatment of shivering after spinal anaesthesia and reported that dexmedetomidine was significantly superior than tramadol with shorter duration of cessation of shivering (mean difference {MD} = -2.14; 95%CI [- 2.79, - 1.49], P < 0.00001, I2 = 98%), lower recurrent rate of shivering (relative risk {RR} = 0.45; 95%CI [0.27, 0.73], P = 0.001) and higher rate of shivering control (RR =1.03; 95%CI [1.01, 1.06], P = 0.01)⁸. Similarly, another study also compared the efficacy of dexmedetomidine against tramadol for treatment of shivering during spinal anaesthesia in patients undergoing caesarean section and reported that duration (in minutes) of cessation of shivering was lower in patients receiving dexmedetomidine (3.8 ± 1.12) as compared to tramadol (5.12 ± 1.27)⁹.

On the other hand, Sarwer *et al.* conducted a study to compare the efficacy of dexmedetomidine with tramadol to

control post-spinal anesthesia shivering along with their associated hemodynamic changes and side effects. They reported that difference between the two drugs was not statistically significant in terms of duration of cessation of post-spinal shivering [dexmedetomidine group 6.20 ± 1.21 minutes versus tramadol group 5.87 ± 1.47 minutes; $p = 0.344$] and recurrence of shivering ($p = 0.161$). However, side effects was higher in tramadol group with 3 out of 30 patients in tramadol group developing bradycardia as compared to 1 out of 30 patients in dexmedetomidine group ($p = 0.301$) while no patient developed hypotension or respiratory depression ¹⁰.

Although, both these drugs are used for management of post-spinal anaesthesia shivering but which of these drugs is superior in efficacy than the other is still debatable due to controversial results of previous studies. Moreover, sub-optimal conditions of temperature control in operating rooms and aberrant drug supply at my study setting makes it imperative to compare the efficacy of dexmedetomidine versus tramadol in management of post-spinal anaesthesia shivering.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

SPINAL ANESTHESIA

Injection of a local anaesthetic into the intrathecal space is required in order to perform the procedure known as spinal anaesthesia, which is a type of regional anaesthesia. Although it was first developed more than a century ago, it continues to be an important anaesthetic method that is applied in a wide variety of therapeutic settings. In order to achieve spinal anaesthesia, a local anaesthetic solution must first be injected into the intrathecal region.

Providing surgical anaesthesia for procedures that take place below the umbilicus can be accomplished with the use of this common anaesthetic method. Because of the area's close proximity to the central nervous system, safe practise is of the utmost importance and calls for an in-depth knowledge of the pertinent anatomy, physiology, and pharmacology. Although complications are uncommon, they must be identified as soon as possible and addressed in a proper manner.

ANATOMY

When administering spinal anaesthesia, a needle is inserted between the lumbar vertebrae and then passed into the dura in order to provide the anaesthetic medicine. The anatomy of the

bony spine and the vertebrae will each be broken down into greater detail below (figure 1 and figure 2)

Fig. 1
Basic vertebral anatomy

Fig. 2
Spine anatomy overview

- **Vertebral level:** Spinal anesthesia is performed no higher than the mid to low lumbar vertebral level to avoid puncturing the spinal cord with the spinal needle. In most patients, the spinal cord terminates as the conus medullaris at the lower border of the first lumbar vertebral body (L1), though it may end lower.¹⁴ Therefore, the spinal needle is inserted at the L3 to L4 or L4 to L5 interspace. Other interspaces, eg L2 to 3 or L5 to S1, may be less ideal; L2 to 3 is close to the spinal cord and injection at L5 to S1

requires greater spread of local anesthetic (LA) to anesthetize thoracic dermatomes, which is necessary for some surgical procedures.

The intercrystal line (ie, the line between the posterior superior iliac crests) is used as a rough guide for spinal needle placement. In many patients, this line crosses the body of L4, though it may cross the spine from L1 to L2 to L4 to L5, and tends to be higher in obese and female patients.¹⁵⁻¹⁶ Because landmarks do not accurately predict the lumbar interspace, the spinal needle should be inserted at or below the intercrystal line.

- Ligaments – The epidural space is the space between the dural sac and the inside of the bony spinal canal. The tough ligamentum flavum forms the posterior border of the epidural space at each interlaminar space. The interspinous ligament stretches between the spinous processes of successive vertebrae, and the supraspinous ligament anchors the tips of the spinous processes in a continuous column
- Meninges – Within the bony vertebral canal, the spinal cord is surrounded by three membranes: the pia mater, the arachnoid mater, and the dura mater (innermost to outmost). The dura and arachnoid

maters loosely adhere to each other in the spinal canal and comprise the "dural sac" in which the spinal cord is suspended. The subarachnoid space within the dural sac is located between the pia and arachnoid maters and contains cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), spinal nerves, and blood vessels. A loose trabecular network exists between the pia and dura-arachnoid.

- CSF - The central nervous system (CNS) is surrounded by CSF, an ultrafiltrate of blood. CSF is formed continuously by the choroid plexuses and serves to protect the brain and spinal cord by providing a cushion. It also serves as a conduit for the delivery of spinal anesthetic agents to the spinal cord. CSF circulates in the spinal canal, with both bulk flow and oscillatory movements. This flow may explain some of the movement of anesthetic agents toward the brain after injection into the lumbar subarachnoid space. The density of CSF at body temperature averages 1.0003 ± 0.0003 g/mL; density relative to the injected LA solution affects the distribution of spinal block.

- Nerves – The dorsal and ventral spinal nerve roots emerge from the spinal cord at each vertebral level and combine to form the spinal nerves. The lumbar and sacral nerve roots extend past the conus medullaris as the cauda equina and exit the vertebral canal between successive lumbar and sacral vertebrae

Autonomic nerves, both sympathetic and parasympathetic, are blocked by spinal anesthesia, in addition to sensory and motor nerves. The extent of sympathetic block depends on the height of the spinal block. Preganglionic sympathetic nerve fibers arise from the intermediolateral tract of the spinal cord from T1 to L2. The axons exit the spinal cord with the ventral nerve root of the spinal nerves and synapse with cell bodies in the ganglion of the sympathetic trunk. Sympathetic cardioaccelerator fibers arise from T1 to T4.

The splanchnic component of the parasympathetic nervous system travels in the ventral roots of S2 to S4 and supplies the organs of the pelvis, including the bladder, reproductive organs, descending colon, and rectum. Thus, all of the sacral parasympathetic nerves are blocked with spinal anesthesia, and

some of the sympathetic nerves are blocked, depending on the cephalad extent of neural block.

- Dermatomes – A dermatome is defined as the cutaneous area supplied by a single spinal nerve root. The term "spinal level" refers to the most cephalad dermatome anesthetized by the spinal anesthetic. The level required for a specific surgery is determined by the dermatome level of the skin incision and by the level required for surgical manipulation; these two requirements may be very different. As an example, a low abdominal incision for cesarean delivery is made at the T11 to T12 dermatome, but a T4 spinal level is required to prevent pain with peritoneal manipulation.

TECHNIQUE

Preparation for spinal anesthesia:

For spinal anesthesia, the standard and emergency anesthesia equipment and medications should be prepared as they would be for general anesthesia.

Most commonly, a disposable spinal kit is used, which contains needles, drugs, labels, and other required equipment. The kit is usually placed on a cart or table on the side of the clinician's dominant hand.

A phenylephrine infusion and a syringe of ephedrine (5 mg/mL) is prepared preoperatively; a high percentage of patients require administration of a vasoconstrictor during spinal anesthesia. Anticholinergic medication (ie, atropine and glycopyrrolate) and epinephrine should be immediately available.

Standard American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) monitors should be applied (ie, blood pressure, electrocardiography, oxygen saturation) prior to initiation of spinal anesthesia. Other monitoring (eg, intraarterial pressure monitoring) and the extent of venous access are dictated by the patient's medical status and the planned procedure.

A preprocedure time-out should be performed, which includes confirmation of the following:

- Patient identifiers (ie, name, medical record number, date of birth)
- Allergies
- Planned surgical procedure
- Surgical and anesthesia consent with site marked, if applicable
- Coagulation status (ie, anticoagulant administration, coagulation laboratory values if applicable)

With the exception of discussion of the patient's coagulation status, these checklist components are a part of the World Health Organization (WHO) Surgical Safety Checklist components performed before the induction of anesthesia.

Premedication:

Light sedation may be administered if necessary prior to spinal needle placement. Deep sedation should be avoided in order to allow patient cooperation with positioning and feedback (eg, the occurrence of pain or paresthesia) during the procedure. Any sedation should be administered in reduced doses, titrated to effect, anticipating the sedation that accompanies spinal block.

Positioning for spinal procedure:

Optimal patient positioning is critical to the success of neuraxial procedures. In this setting, the goals of positioning are

to avoid rotation of the spine and to create a straight path for needle insertion between the bones of the spine. Flexion of the spine opens the space between the spinous processes and is most important when a midline approach is used.

The sitting and lateral decubitus positions are used most commonly and are chosen according to clinician preference, planned patient position during the surgical procedure, patient body habitus, and patient comfort. As an example, the lateral position may be used for a patient with a hip fracture, with the fracture side up. The jackknife position (ie, prone with hips flexed) is occasionally used for spinal anesthesia placement when this will be the position for surgery (eg, for rectal procedures).

The clinician can stand or sit to perform the procedure; the table height and patient position should be adjusted to prevent the need for the clinician to bend or reach.

Sitting position:

The sitting position is most common and may be particularly useful for larger patients in whom the bony landmarks are difficult to feel; if the patient sits straight and level, the midline may be easier to estimate compared with the lateral position. The sitting position is usually preferred for very low sacral spinal anesthesia with hyperbaric local anesthetic (LA) drugs (ie, saddle block).

In the sitting position, the patient's legs should hang off the side of the bed, with the feet planted on a nonmobile stool. The backs of the knees should be against the edge of the bed so that the patient's back is as close as possible to the clinician standing on the other side of the bed. The patient is asked to "slouch" symmetrically with shoulders over the hips to allow flexion of the lumbar spine. Usually the patient sits with the arms bent at the elbows with forearms and hands resting lightly on the thighs. Alternatively, the patient can rest the arms on a padded Mayo stand; the patient should not lean forward, which would increase the lumbar lordosis. In addition, positioning aids are available that are designed to support the patient in the sitting position during neuraxial block.

Lateral decubitus position:

Either left or right lateral decubitus position can be used and may be chosen based on the baricity of the spinal drug preparation. As an example, if hyperbaric medication is used for a left leg procedure, the patient should be positioned with the left side down. If baricity relative to surgical position is not a concern, the left lateral position is usually more comfortable for a right-handed clinician.

The patient's back should be close to the edge of the table nearest the clinician, parallel to the edge of the bed and vertical, with the hips aligned one above the other. The thighs are drawn up with the hips maximally flexed, and the patient is asked to "push out" or "round" the lower back. Patients instructed to "curl up" often actually curl their upper back, and since the bottom shoulder is fixed to the mattress, this results in rotation of the spine. The dependent shoulder may need to be pulled forward by an assistant. Patients with broad hips may require a pillow under and between the legs in order to prevent forward tilting.

Prone position:

This position is occasionally used for spinal anesthesia for rectal or pilonidal surgery. The patient is positioned on chest supports, with the hips flexed (ie, the jackknife position). In this setting, hypobaric or isobaric spinal medication is used to primarily anesthetize low lumbar and sacral nerve roots.

Pre procedure ultrasonography:

Routinely preprocedural ultrasonography is used in patients whose anatomic landmarks are difficult to palpate. Preprocedural ultrasonography is increasingly used to help define anatomy prior to spinal anesthesia. Ultrasound can be used to identify the interspace for needle placement, and to estimate the depth of the

subarachnoid space, particularly in obese patients or those with difficult anatomy.¹⁸⁻²⁵ A curved array low-frequency (2 to 5 MHz) is commonly used and the back is scanned in both the parasagittal and transverse planes.²⁶ The midline and lumbar interspinous spaces are identified and marked on the back, the depth to the subarachnoid space is estimated, and the spinal needle is inserted in the marked space.

A 2020 systematic review and meta-analysis of preprocedural ultrasound use before attempted neuraxial anesthesia compared with the traditional palpation technique in obstetric patients (18 studies, 1844 patients) found that ultrasound use was associated with increased first needle pass rate success in patients with perceived difficult anatomy, but not in patients whose surface landmarks were easy to palpate.²⁷ Use of ultrasonography was associated with longer time to identify the interspace, but there was no difference in procedural time or failure rate between landmark and ultrasound techniques.

Studies have shown that use of ultrasound is associated with more accurate identification of the lumbar interspace than palpation.²⁸ Large studies are needed to determine whether this improves the safety of spinal anesthesia.

Aseptic technique:

Strict aseptic technique is required for all aspects of the spinal anesthesia procedure. In 2017, the ASA published a Practice Advisory for the Prevention, Diagnosis, and Management of Infectious Complications Associated with Neuraxial Techniques.²⁹ The critical components of the Practice Advisory are agreed, including the following:

- The clinician should: Wear a cap and mask, covering mouth and nose, Remove jewelry, including rings and watches, Wash hands prior to the procedure, Wear sterile gloves,

The skin of the patient's back should be: Widely cleaned using individual antiseptic packets of chlorhexidine, preferably with alcohol, allowing adequate time for the solution to dry, according to the antiseptic package insert. The skin prep solution should be discarded before opening the spinal tray and preparing the drug solutions. Contamination of equipment with the prep solution must be avoided to prevent introduction of neurotoxic solution into the subarachnoid space.

- Draped with a sterile drape.

At the author's institution, additional precautions include:

- Change masks between cases
- In addition to removing jewelry, remove false fingernails

- Wash hands with alcohol solution or perform surgical scrub
- All providers in the immediate environment wear a cap and mask
- The patient wears a cap
- Clean the tops of nonsterile drug ampules with alcohol or chlorhexidine

Choice of spinal needle:

Usually a small-diameter (ie, 24 to 27 gauge) pencil-point spinal needle is used with an introducer needle for spinal anesthesia. Larger-diameter needles and cutting needle tips³⁰⁻³¹ are both associated with an increased risk of postdural puncture headache (PDPH) compared with smaller-diameter and pencil-point needles.³²

Disposable needles are used for spinal anesthesia. All spinal needles have a close-fitting, removable stylet that prevents skin and subcutaneous tissue from plugging the needle during insertion. Spinal needles are available in various gauges (ie, needle diameter) and with several needle tip shapes, as well as various lengths for use in larger patients.

Spinal needles can be classified according to the needle tip, as follows:

- Cutting-tip needles – Quincke spinal needles have sharp cutting tips, with the hole at the end of the needle.
- Pencil-point needles – Whitacre and Sprotte needles have a closed tip shaped like that of a pencil, with the hole on the side of the needle near the tip. These needles are designed to minimize leak of cerebrospinal fluid after puncture and reduce the chance of PDPH.

An introducer needle is usually used to place the higher-gauge (ie, smaller-diameter, 24 to 27 gauge) spinal needles. These fine needles are very flexible and more difficult to direct through tissue than lower-gauge (greater-diameter) needles. The introducer needle is used to puncture the skin and is inserted into the interspinous ligament, when a midline approach is used, along the desired needle path. The spinal needle is then inserted through it.

A stiffer, larger-diameter spinal needle (ie, 22 gauge) may be required for older patients, in whom spinal needle placement may be more challenging. These patients are often unable to flex the lumbar spine and may have calcified ligaments that make the use of fine needles difficult or impossible. In addition, older patients are at lower risk for PDPH than younger patients regardless of spinal needle size.³³ In this setting, a 24 or 25 gauge

pencil-point needle is tried and use a 22 gauge needle if necessary.

Approaches:

The spinal needle can be inserted using a midline or a paramedian approach. The midline approach is simpler; the paramedian approach requires mental triangulation and an estimate of the depth from the skin to the dura. However, the midline approach may be unsuccessful in patients who are unable to flex the spine to open the space between adjacent spinous processes. Paramedian needle placement requires less spinal flexion.

For either approach, the needle is usually inserted at the L4 to L5 or L3 to L4 interspace. In most patients, a line between the iliac crests crosses the body of L4 or the L4 to L5 interspace.

Midline approach technique:

The aim is to place the spinal needle precisely in the midline, which is usually defined by the spinous processes with optimal positioning. The procedure is performed as follows:

- Palpate the interspace between two spinous processes at the chosen spinal level. With a 25 gauge needle, raise a skin wheal with 1% lidocaine, in the midline of the spine, in the

lower third of the interspace. Infiltrate the subcutaneous tissue with lidocaine into the interspinous ligament.

- Insert an introducer needle at a slight cephalad angle, through the supraspinous ligament, until slightly firm tissue is felt, suggesting that the tip is in the interspinous ligament.
- Insert the 24 to 27 gauge spinal needle into and through the introducer needle. The needle passes through the ligamentum flavum, followed by the epidural space, and then the dura-arachnoid. Changes in resistance are felt as the needle passes through each of these layers. A pop is often felt when the dura is pierced. The depth of the dura from the skin in patients of normal body habitus is 5.1 ± 1.0 cm.³⁴
- After a pop or loss of resistance is appreciated, remove the stylet and watch for cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) flow into and through the hub of the needle. CSF flow may be very slow through fine-gauge needles, particularly if the patient is in the lateral position.

If CSF does not appear, rotate the needle (only if pencil-point needle) and, if necessary, adjust the needle tip (eg,

advance, redirect, or withdraw the needle and repeat the procedure).

- If the needle hits bone during spinal needle placement, note the depth, withdraw the needle into the introducer, redirect and reinsert in a slightly cephalad direction. If bone is contacted again, redirect as follows:
 - If bone is contacted at a shallower depth, the needle is likely contacting the more cephalad spinous process in the interspace, and should then be redirected in a caudad direction.
 - If bone is contacted deeper, the needle is likely contacting the more caudad spinous process in the interspace, and the needle should then be redirected in an even more cephalad direction.
 - If bone is contacted at the same depth, the needle is likely contacting lamina, and the tip is off the midline. The midline should be reassessed, and the needle redirected accordingly. The patient can often report that he/she perceives the needle to one side or the other.

- If using a 20 or 22 gauge spinal needle, perform the procedure in the same way without an introducer needle.

Paramedian approach technique:

The paramedian approach is often used for patients who are unable to flex the spine, or when the midline approach fails.

- Palpate the interspace between two spinous processes at the chosen spinal level. With a 25 gauge needle, raise a skin wheal with 1% lidocaine one centimeter lateral to the midline at the cephalad border of the inferior spinous process. Infiltrate the subcutaneous tissue with lidocaine.
- Insert the introducer needle at a 10 to 15 degree angle from the midline in a slightly cephalad direction (ie, 75 to 80 degrees from skin). The aim is to puncture the dura in the midline. With this approach, the introducer does not pass through the supraspinous or interspinous ligaments.
- Insert a 24 to 27 gauge spinal needle through the introducer needle and advance through the tough ligamentum flavum until a pop is felt as the needle pierces the dura.
- Remove the stylet and watch for CSF flow into and through the hub of the needle. CSF flow may be very slow through the very fine-gauge needles.

If CSF does not appear, rotate the needle and, if necessary, adjust the needle tip (eg, advance, redirect, or withdraw the needle and repeat the procedure).

- If the needle hits bone, it is most likely vertebral lamina. Withdraw the needle into the introducer, redirect slightly, and advance the spinal needle again. Several attempts at passing the needle may be required.
- If using a 20 or 22 gauge spinal needle, perform the procedure in the same way without an introducer needle.

Spinal injection:

Once CSF flows to the end of the spinal needle, the LA solution is injected.

- Stabilize the spinal needle to prevent movement while connecting the LA syringe to the hub of the spinal needle. We place the lateral edge of the nondominant hand against the patient's back, using the index finger and thumb to hold the needle hub while connecting the syringe.
- After securely connecting the LA syringe, aspirate approximately 0.2 mL of CSF into the syringe to confirm subarachnoid placement of the needle tip.
- Inject the LA solution slowly, at a rate of ≤ 0.5 mL/second.

- Although the practice is not evidence-based, many clinicians aspirate approximately 0.2 mL after completing the injection to confirm that the needle tip remained correctly positioned through injection. Other clinicians aspirate a small amount of CSF halfway through the injection, reasoning that it is too late to reposition the needle if the need to do so is discovered at the end of the injection. If CSF is aspirated, it should be reinjected.
- Remove the introducer, spinal needle, and syringe as one unit.

Post-injection positioning:

The timing and specifics of patient positioning after anesthetic injection depend on the required level of block, the baricity of the spinal solution, and the position used for the spinal injection.

HYPERBARIC SPINAL DRUGS:

If a hyperbaric solution is injected for a perineal surgical procedure, the patient should be left sitting for several minutes to allow the anesthetic solution to sink to the sacral nerve roots to achieve what is called a "saddle block." In contrast, if a high thoracic spinal level is required, the patient should be placed in

the supine position immediately after injection. The tilt of the operating table should be adjusted based on the level of the block.

Isobaric or hypobaric drug:

If a plain (slightly hypobaric) solution is injected in the sitting position, or in the lateral position for bilateral surgery, the patient should be placed supine immediately after injection. If a plain solution is injected in the lateral position for surgery on the nondependent side (eg, hip replacement), the patient should remain in the lateral position and positioned for surgery.

Continuous spinal:

Spinal anesthesia is usually initiated as a single-shot technique. However, occasionally, clinicians site a catheter in the subarachnoid space to enable prolongation of anesthesia by the intermittent injection of local anesthetic solution. Most clinicians use an epidural needle and catheter for continuous spinal anesthesia. The epidural needle is advanced as described for spinal anesthesia. After the needle tip has punctured the dura, the epidural needle stylet is removed and the epidural catheter is inserted through the needle and advanced 2 to 4 cm into the subarachnoid space. The epidural needle is carefully withdrawn without moving the catheter, the epidural catheter connector is secured to the catheter, and CSF is allowed to backflow through

the catheter to the hub of the epidural catheter connector (this is important so that the air in the dead space of the catheter is not injected into the subarachnoid space). The dead space of an epidural catheter is approximately 0.3 mL, and this volume must be taken into account when injecting the spinal anesthetic solution. Drugs used for continuous spinal anesthesia mimic those used for single-shot spinal anesthesia.

Advantages of the continuous spinal technique include the option to titrate the initial dose, and the maintenance of anesthesia for a prolonged period. Usually the initial dose is decreased to one-half to two-thirds of the usual single-shot dose and then titrate to effect. Additional doses of anesthetic solution can be injected as needed to prolong the block.

The use of continuous spinal anesthesia has fallen out of favor because of reports of neurologic complications, including cauda equina syndrome when LA was administered through small-gauge catheters (28 gauge, so-called microcatheters) for continuous spinal anesthesia,³⁵ and because of the high risk of PDPH using larger-gauge catheters. A large retrospective study of continuous spinal anesthesia reported a 33.1 percent incidence of PDPH in obstetric patients who received continuous spinal with a microcatheter (28 gauge).³⁶

A continuous spinal catheter is now commercially available in the United States, though experience with its use is limited.³⁷⁻³⁸

Choice of spinal drugs:

For single-shot spinal anesthesia, LAs and adjuvant medications must be chosen to achieve the required spinal level and duration of anesthesia and recovery. Particularly for ambulatory procedures, time to micturition and ambulation are critical to a satisfactory perioperative experience. The most important determinants of the extent of sensory block are the dose and baricity (relative to the patient's position) of the anesthetic solution. Less important variables include patient age, body mass index, orientation of the pencil-point spinal needle orifice, and the angle of the needle relative to the neuraxis.³⁹

Baricity:

Baricity refers to the ratio of the density of a solution to the density of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). Solutions with the same density as CSF have a baricity of 1 and are called isobaric. Solutions denser than CSF are called hyperbaric; those less dense than CSF are called hypobaric.

Baricity influences the distribution of anesthetic solution within the subarachnoid space; hyperbaric solutions tend to "sink"

within the CSF relative to the site of injection, and hypobaric solutions rise relative to the site of injection, while gravity has no effect on the distribution of isobaric solutions in CSF. Thus, the patient's position during and after injection of spinal drugs influences the extent of spinal block with hyperbaric or hypobaric drugs.

The baricity of the anesthetic solution, along with the patient's position, can be used to increase the density and duration of spinal block at the site of surgery. As an example, a saddle block (ie, low lumbar and sacral nerve block) can be achieved by injecting a hyperbaric solution in the sitting position and keeping the patient sitting for several minutes. Conversely, spinal anesthesia for rectal surgery can be performed with a hypobaric solution injected with the patient in a jackknife position.

LA solutions are made hyperbaric by adding dextrose to LA (eg, bupivacaine 0.75% in 8.25% dextrose is commercially available). A hypobaric solution can be mixed by adding sterile water to a plain solution of LA (eg, bupivacaine 0.5% in saline). LA solutions in saline are slightly hypobaric but behave and are used clinically as if they are isobaric.

In general, hyperbaric solutions result in faster onset, greater extent of sensory block, and shorter duration of block

compared with isobaric solutions.⁴⁰ A double-blinded study of duration and extent of spinal anesthesia that randomized patients to receive hyperbaric drug (0.5% bupivacaine with 5 or 8% glucose) or minimally hypobaric drug (plain 0.5% bupivacaine) found that the hyperbaric solutions produced greater cephalad spread of block compared with the hypobaric drug (ie, T6 versus T10).⁴¹

Local anesthetics:

Bupivacaine is the most commonly used LA for spinal anesthesia in the United States. Others include lidocaine, tetracaine, ropivacaine, and 2-chloroprocaine. Not all of the clinically used formulations of LAs have been approved for intrathecal injection by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA), though they have a record of safety when used for spinal anesthesia. Only preservative-free preparations of LAs and other adjuvants should be used for spinal anesthesia.

All LAs are neurotoxic in high concentrations. However, when mixed with preservative-free water, saline, or dextrose solutions to achieve the concentrations used clinically, neurotoxicity is rare.

Studies of the clinical characteristics of spinal LAs usually measure two-dermatome regression of sensory blockade as an

indicator of duration of surgical anesthesia. Time to two dermatome regression is approximately the same as the duration of surgical anesthesia; the density of neuroblockade wanes from the corresponding surgical dermatomes simultaneously with regression of cephalad sensory blockade. By the time the cephalad extent of sensory blockade has regressed two dermatomes, the density of neuroblockade at the site of surgery is inadequate for surgical anesthesia.

Bupivacaine:

Bupivacaine is a long-acting amide LA. Bupivacaine is our LA of choice for spinal anesthesia for cesarean delivery, lower extremity joint arthroplasty, and urologic and gynecologic pelvic procedures. Although low-dose bupivacaine (eg, 4 to 6 mg) has been described for outpatient anesthesia, the prolonged recovery time relative to shorter-acting LAs or general anesthesia makes bupivacaine less desirable for ambulatory surgery.

Dose:

Doses of bupivacaine range from 6 to 15 mg (eg, cesarean delivery 12 mg; lower extremity joint arthroplasty 12.5 to 15 mg)

Duration:

Duration of surgical anesthesia – 1.5 to 2.5 hours

Available formulations:

Hyperbaric 0.75% in 8.25% dextrose, slightly hypobaric 0.5% in saline

Tetracaine:

Tetracaine is a long-acting ester LA that was commonly used several decades ago. Although tetracaine is still used in some centers, it has largely been replaced with bupivacaine.

- Dose – 5 to 20 mg
- Duration of surgical anesthesia/two-dermatome regression – 1.5 to 2.5 hours
- Available formulations – 1% solution, slightly hypobaric

SHIVERING

Postoperative shivering is a common complication of anaesthesia. Shivering is believed to increase oxygen consumption, increase the risk of hypoxemia, induce lactic acidosis, and catecholamine release. Therefore, it might increase the postoperative complications especially in high-risk patients. Moreover, shivering is one of the leading causes of discomfort for postsurgical patients.

Shivering is usually triggered by hypothermia. However, it occurs even in normothermic patients during the perioperative

period. The aetiology of shivering has been understood insufficiently. Another potential mechanism is pain and acute opioid withdrawal (especially with the use of short-acting narcotics). Besides that shivering is poorly understood, the gold standard for the treatment and prevention has not been defined yet. Perioperative hypothermia prevention is the first method to avoid shivering. Many therapeutic strategies for treating shivering exist and most are empiric. Unfortunately, the overall quality of the anti-shivering guidelines is low.

Two main strategies are available: pharmacological and non-pharmacological anti-shivering methods. The combination of forced-air warming devices and intravenous meperidine is the most validated method. We also analyzed different medications but final conclusion about the optimal anti-shivering medication is difficult to be drawn due to the lack of high-quality evidence. Nevertheless, control of PS is possible and clinically effective with simple pharmacological interventions combined with non-pharmacological methods.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY ASPECTS:

The fundamental tremor frequency on the electromyogram in humans is typically near 200 Hz. This basal frequency is

modulated by a slow, 4-8 cycles/ min, waxing-and-waning pattern.⁴²⁻⁴³ In 1972 Soliman et al. found two different patterns of shivering: a tonic pattern similar to normal shivering, and a phasic wave pattern similar to a pathologic clone. In 1991, Sessler et al. published that both patterns (tonic and clonic) were thermoregulatory in volunteers.⁴³⁻⁴⁴

The tonic pattern showed a constant sinusoide form of normal shivering and it seems to be a thermoregulatory answer to the intraoperative hypothermia. By contrast, the clonic pattern is not a normal component of thermoregulatory shivering and it seems to be specific of recovery from volatile anaesthesia. This pattern of shivering might come from the lost of inhibition produced by general anaesthesia in the control of spinal reflexes. Shivering is elicited when the preoptic region of the hypothalamus is cooled. Efferent signals mediating shivering descend in the medial forebrain bundle.

Spinal alpha motor neurons and their axons are the final common path for both coordinated movement and shivering.⁴⁵ A typical cold tremor has a specific rhythm in the form of grouped discharges in the electromyography. During continued cold stimulation of the skin or the spinal cord, motor neurons are recruited in a sequence of increasing size, starting with the small

gamma motor neurons that are followed by the small tonic alpha motor neurons, and finally, the larger phasic alpha motor neurons.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁷ In other studies with surgical patients, not volunteers, research demonstrated a different incidence of non-thermoregulatory shivering in normothermic postoperative patients.⁴⁸

A tonic stiffening pattern of muscular activity was observed as a non-temperature dependent effect of isoflurane anaesthesia. Another observed pattern was a spontaneous electromyographic clonus that required both hypothermia and residual isoflurane end-tidal concentrations between 0.4 and 0.2%.⁴³ Mathew et al. describe the following shivering score which assesses the severity of shivering. 0: no shivering; 1: mild fasciculations of face and neck and electrocardiography (ECG) disturbances in the absence of voluntary activity of the arms; 2: visible tremor in the muscle group; 3: gross muscular activity involving the entire body.⁴⁹

AETIOLOGY

The combination of anaesthetic-induced thermoregulatory impairment and exposure to a cool environment makes most unwarmed surgical patients hypothermic. Shivering is usually triggered by hypothermia. However, it occurs even in

normothermic patients during the perioperative period. The aetiology of shivering has not been understood sufficiently.

While cold induced thermoregulatory shivering remains an obvious aetiology, the phenomenon has also been attributed to numerous other causes: pain, disinhibited spine reflexes, decreased sympathetic activity, respiratory alkalosis. The conventional explanation for postanaesthetic tremor is that anaesthetic induced thermoregulatory inhibition abruptly dissipates, thus increasing the shivering threshold towards normal. Discrepancy between the persistent low body temperature and the now, near-normal threshold activates simple thermoregulatory shivering. Difficulties with this proposed explanation include the observations that tremor frequently is not observed in markedly hypothermic patients and that tremor occurs commonly in normothermic patients.⁵⁰

Perioperative hypothermia is defined as a core temperature, 33°C to 35°C, while the shivering threshold in nonanaesthetized patients is 35.5°C. Anaesthetic agents increase the heat response thresholds and decrease the cold response thresholds so that the normal inter threshold range (hypothalamic set point) is increased.⁵¹ However, the study of Sessler et al⁴³ suggested that special factors related to surgery, stress or pain, might contribute

to the genesis of postoperative tremor because they failed to identify any shivering-like activity in normothermic volunteers. Pain might facilitate shivering in both postoperative patients and in women having spontaneous term labor. The mechanism of thermoregulation is tightly linked to other homeostatic systems, including the control of pain. Pain and temperature signals are transmitted along similar fiber systems that synapse in dorsal horn regions. Rostral ventromedial medulla regulates analgesia to noxious stimuli and has a thermoregulatory response to peripheral warming and cooling.

One of the important functions of the rostral ventromedial medulla is to modulate the amount of pain and temperature input ascending from the spinal cord by gating the transmission of neuronal signals at the level of the dorsal horns.⁵² In general, instead of the commonly held view of a single thermoregulatory integrator (i.e., the preoptic area of the hypothalamus) with multiple inputs and outputs, modern concepts include integrators for each thermoregulatory response. Furthermore, these integrators are distributed among numerous levels within the nervous system, with each being facilitated or inhibited by levels above and below. Therefore, shivering can be divided into two types.⁵³ The most common type is thermoregulatory shivering,

which correlates with cutaneous vasoconstriction in response to hypothermia. In contrast, approximately 15% of shivering responses is from non-thermoregulatory shivering, which is associated with cutaneous vasodilation and possibly with pain.⁵⁴

More recent studies have also reported an increased incidence of PS after remifentanil administration.⁵⁵ Remifentanil was associated with an increased incidence of postoperative shivering compared with alfentanil or fentanyl, but no significant difference was seen when compared with sufentanil.

In this case the mechanisms underlying are considered to include acute opioid tolerance of short-acting narcotics, which is closely related to the activation of the N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor. Nakasuji et al. compared two doses of remifentanil and concluded that remifentanil-induced PS is not a phenomenon of intraoperative hypothermia. The higher incidence of PS with higher doses of remifentanil probably reflects acute opioid tolerance and stimulation of N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors, similar to hyperalgesia.⁵⁶ The author developed three mechanisms that may account for PS after remifentanil administration.

First, remifentanil is eliminated faster than other opioids. Opioids inhibit thermoregulatory responses; thus shivering does

not occur during surgery because the threshold of shivering decreases below body temperature.⁵⁷ The threshold might return to normal immediately after discontinuance of remifentanil due to the drug's kinetics. When the threshold increases faster than the increase in body temperature during recovery from general anaesthesia, shivering is triggered.

The second mechanism is related to pain; in fact, remifentanil at high doses induced PS more frequently than at low doses. This result is in accordance with hyperalgesia caused by high doses of remifentanil in previous studies. In consequence, patients who are administered high doses of remifentanil are sensitive to shivering after sudden discontinuation.⁵⁶ Another mechanism is that shivering is a sign of opioid withdrawal caused by acute tolerance. Short-acting opioids like remifentanil could cause opioid tolerance and hyperalgesia, especially when higher doses are administered continuously. The NMDA receptors are thought to play a major role in the development of acute opioid tolerance because remifentanil-induced hyperalgesia can be prevented by low doses of ketamine, a typical NMDA antagonist. It was speculated that remifentanil stimulates the NMDA receptors and glycine as an additive in the remifentanil dose could

directly stimulate NMDA receptors and prophylactic ketamine was reported to be effective to prevent PS.⁵⁸

In addition, magnesium is a non-competitive NMDA receptor antagonist and intraoperative infusion of magnesium sulphate reduced PS.⁵⁹ Regarding shivering post neuroaxial anaesthesia the mechanism might be different. Both neuraxial (epidural and spinal anaesthesia) and general anaesthesia are associated with a significant incidence of shivering, and the incidence is 40%-60% in regional anaesthetic patients and up to 60% in general anaesthetic ones.⁶⁰

Shivering differs from general anaesthesia to neuraxial anaesthesia. General anaesthesia could impair the central thermoregulation, but spinal anaesthesia affects central and peripheral thermoregulation, by enlarging the interthreshold range via raising the sweating threshold and decreasing the vasoconstriction and shivering thresholds. The core temperature decrease will be in a plateau after 3-4 h in general anaesthesia but in the neuraxial anaesthesia there is no plateau, because in neuroaxial anaesthesia the vasoconstriction will not be evoked when the core temperature triggers the reset vasoconstriction threshold, in contrast with general anaesthesia. Thus, more heat will be lost, and more incidences will occur in neuraxial

anaesthesia. For instance, the primary mechanism of perioperative hypothermia during caesarean delivery under spinal anaesthesia is because of redistribution of the intravascular volume from the core to peripheral compartment below the level of sympathectomy, predisposing the body to radiant heat loss.⁶¹

Beside this, spinal anaesthesia itself slightly decreases the threshold-for triggering vasoconstriction and shivering above the level of the block. In addition, Doufas and colleagues reported slight decreases in thresholds during epidural anaesthesia based on an apparent increase in lower body skin temperature.⁶²

PS has been anecdotally observed to be frequent and severe in cannabis smokers following general anaesthesia. It has been suggested that cannabis has analgesic effects mediated via CB1 receptors in synergy with opioid and noradrenergic receptors (alpha-2 effects). Moreover, there is a suggestion that pain and temperature signals are transmitted along similar fiber systems in the dorsal horn of the spinal cord. Cannabis has been shown to interfere with both thermogenic and nonthermogenic mechanisms of PS.⁵¹

The treatment of shivering includes both pharmacological and non-pharmacological methods. The non-pharmacological management is by external heating like the use of forced air

warming, warming blankets, warmed fluids etc., According to the results of a meta-analysis, the most frequently reported pharmacological interventions include clonidine, pethidine, tramadol, nefopam and ketamine. Unfortunately, no gold standard treatment is known for shivering as the administration of all the available drugs is associated with various adverse effects.

During the last decade, Tramadol has become a favoured and commonly used drug for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering. However, it has many adverse effects like nausea, vomiting, dizziness etc., which cause further discomfort to the patient.⁶³⁻⁶⁴ Clonidine is another agent which has gained popularity during the last few years. Various studies, which have been conducted to compare them have concluded that clonidine has better efficacy and less adverse effects as compared to tramadol.⁶³⁻⁶⁴ But there was 5-10% incidence of hypotension and bradycardia with clonidine.⁶³

Dexmedetomidine, a congener of clonidine, is a highly selective α_2 -adrenoceptor agonist. It has been used as a sedative agent and is known to reduce the shivering threshold.⁶⁵ Few studies which have explored its anti-shivering potential have inferred that dexmedetomidine is an effective drug without any

major adverse effect and provides good haemodynamic stability.⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷ Hence, we planned to do a comparative study of the efficacy, haemodynamic, and adverse effects of tramadol and dexmedetomidine when used for the control of post-spinal anaesthesia shivering.

Geeta Mittal and others⁶⁸ evaluated and compare the efficacy, haemodynamic and adverse effects of dexmedetomidine with those of tramadol, when used for control of post-spinal anaesthesia shivering. It was revealed that time taken for cessation of shivering was significantly less with dexmedetomidine when compared to tramadol. Nausea and vomiting was observed only in tramadol group (28% and; 20% respectively). There was not much difference in the sedation profile of both the drugs.

It was concluded that although both drugs are effective, the time taken for cessation of shivering is less with dexmedetomidine when compared to tramadol. Moreover, dexmedetomidine has negligible adverse effects, whereas tramadol is associated with significant nausea and vomiting.

Alpha-2 adrenergic agonists are widely used nowadays in anaesthesia and intensive care settings. Dexmedetomidine is an α_2 adrenoceptor agonist, with antihypertensive, sedative,

analgesic, and anti-shivering properties.⁶⁹ The anti-shivering effects of alpha adrenoceptor agonists are mediated by binding to α_2 receptors that mediate vasoconstriction and the anti-shivering effect. In addition, it has hypothalamic thermoregulatory effects.⁷⁰ Dexmedetomidine comparably reduces the vasoconstriction and shivering thresholds, thus suggesting that it acts on the central thermoregulatory system rather than preventing shivering peripherally.⁷¹

It has been successfully used as an adjunct to local anaesthetics in spinal anaesthesia and peripheral nerve blockade, for the sedation of mechanically ventilated patients in the Intensive Care Unit, as well as supplementation of post-operative analgesia.⁶⁹ The role of dexmedetomidine in the treatment of shivering has been evaluated in a few studies.⁶⁵ It may be a good choice because of its dual effects related 'anti-shivering' and sedation.

With same dose, that is, 0.5 mg/kg of tramadol, the response rate reported by Shukla et al. was 92.5%, by Reddy and Chiruvella as 95.56% and by Tsai and Chu, 87%.⁶³⁻⁶⁴ It was found 100% response rate in our study. Maheshwari et al. reported similar recurrence rate with tramadol as in our study (8%) but the dose used in their study was 1 mg/kg.⁷² The recurrence rate

in the study by Shukla et al. was 5%, which is similar to these results. The incidence of nausea and vomiting with tramadol in our study was 28% and 20%, respectively. The results correspond with that of other studies by Reddy and Chiruvella, Tsai and Chu; Bansal and Jain.^{64,73,74}

However, in the study by Shukla et al⁶³ the incidence of nausea was quite high (77.5%), whereas Wason et al. have reported the incidence of nausea as only 4%.²⁵ These variations could be explained by the peculiar patient characteristics in different studies. Maheshwari et al. have reported a very high incidence of sedation to the extent of 84%, which as mentioned earlier could be due to the higher dose as opposed to 28% sedation in our study.⁷²

THE ORIGINAL STUDY

OBJECTIVES

- To compare the outcome of dexmedetomidine with tramadol for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Outcome:

- It was assessed in terms of time taken for cessation of shivering primarily. Secondary parameters included recurrence of shivering, severity of shivering and side effects.

Side Effects:

- It includes bradycardia, hypotension and respiratory depression.

Recurrence of Shivering:

- It refers to time between cessation of shivering after administration of drug to recurrence of shivering (maximum 1 hour after drug administration).

Severity of Shivering:

It is categorized into 5 grades:

- Grade 0 = no post-spinal anaesthesia shivering.
- Grade 1 = pilo-erection/peripheral vasoconstriction without visible muscle activity.
- Grade 2 = visible muscular activity confined to single group of muscles.
- Grade 3 = visible muscular activity in more than one group of muscles.

- Grade 4 = involvement of whole body.

Bradycardia:

- It refers to heart rate less than 60/min ¹¹

Hypotension:

- It refers to BP less than 90/60 ¹²

Respiratory Depression:

- It refers to respiratory rate less 8/min ¹³

HYPOTHESIS

- Null hypothesis is that there is no difference in efficacy of both drugs for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering
- Alternate hypothesis is that dexmedetomidine has greater efficacy and lesser side effects (bradycardia, hypotension, respiratory depression) as compared to tramadol for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering

METHODS AND MATERIALS

STUDY DESIGN:

- A randomized controlled trial

STUDY SETTING:

- Department of Anaesthesiology, Bolan Medical College, Quetta.

STUDY DURATION:

- 6 months after approval of synopsis

From: _____ to _____

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

- Non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used.

SAMPLE SIZE:

- It was calculated using WHO sample size calculator software with following parameters:
 - Level of significance (α) = 5%
 - Power ($1-\beta$) = 99%
 - Expected duration (in minutes) of cessation of shivering by dexmedetomidine (μ_0) = 3.8 ± 1.12^9
 - Expected duration (in minutes) of cessation of shivering by tramadol (μ_a) = 5.12 ± 1.27^9

Calculated sample size is 70 with 35 patients in group D (dexmedetomidine group) and 35 patients in group T (tramadol group).

SAMPLE SELECTION

Inclusion Criteria

American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) status I-II patients aged 18-40 years, of any gender, who undergo elective surgery under spinal anaesthesia, develop post-spinal anaesthesia shivering of grade 1 or more are were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Following patients were excluded from the study:

1. Patient with known hypersensitivity to dexmedetomidine and tramadol.
2. Patients with pre-existing cardiac, pulmonary, renal or hepatic disease.
3. Patients with hyperthyroidism, Parkinson's disease, psychiatric illness.
4. Patients with history of substance abuse.

DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUE

After approval of study from CPSP and obtaining informed consent of the patients, those aged 18-40 years, of any gender,

who undergo elective surgery under spinal anaesthesia, develop post-spinal anaesthesia shivering of grade 1 or more and are American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) status I-II were included in the study. Patients were randomly assigned to one of two groups using lottery method.

- Group D was given intravenous dexmedetomidine 0.5mcg/kg mixed in 10ml normal saline given slowly over 10 minutes.
- Group T was given intravenous tramadol 0.5mg/kg mixed in 10ml normal saline given slowly over 10 minutes.

It was made sure that temperature of operation room is kept comfortable between 24-26⁰ C. Patients were then assessed for grade of shivering, time taken for cessation of shivering and recurrence of shivering (if any). Furthermore, side effects associated with these drugs were also documented including hypotension, bradycardia and respiratory depression. All the data was documented on performa. Patient anonymity and confidentiality was maintained with utmost priority. No personal identifiers such as "patient registration number" or "Patient name or contact details" were included in documentation.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data was analyzed using SPSS software 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). The numeric variable (age, time of cessation of shivering) was expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. The categorical variables (gender, occurrence, and recurrence of shivering, grade of shivering) were represented as frequency and percentages. Chi-square test was used as test of significance for categorical variables. Independent t-test was used for numerical variables and keeping p-value at ≤ 0.05 .

RESULTS

A total of 70 (35 in each group) fulfilling the selection criteria were enrolled to compare the outcome of dexmedetomidine with tramadol for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering.

Age distribution showed that 24(68.6%) in Group D and 22(62.9%) in Group T were between 18-30 years of age whereas 11(31.4%) in Group D and 13(37.1%) were between 31-40 years of age, mean age in Group D was 29.8 ± 4.47 year and 30.57 ± 4.74 years in Group T. (Table 1)

Gender distribution shows that 6(17.1%) in Group D and 10(28.6%) in Group T were male whereas 29(82.9%) in Group D and 25(71.4%) in Group were females. (Table 2)

Comparison of mean shivering duration was recorded as 3.74 ± 1.06 in Group D whereas 4.97 ± 1.22 in Group T, p-value=0.0001 (Table 3).

Comparison of grade of shivering was recorded as grade 1 in 18(51.4%) in Group D and 3(8.6%) in Group T, grade 2 was recorded in 14(40%) in Group D and 23(65.7%) in Group T. 3(8.6%) in Group D and 9(25.7%) in Group T had Grade 3 shivering. (Table 4)

Recurrence of shivering was recorded as 6(17.1%) in Group D and 9(25.7%) in Group T. (Table 5)

The data was stratified for age, gender, Grade of shivering, and recurrence of shivering. (Table 6-9)

Table 1
Age distribution
(n=70)

Age (in years)	Group D (n=35)		Group T(n=35)	
	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%
18-30	24	68.6	22	62.9
31-40	11	31.4	13	37.1
Total	35	100	35	100
Mean±SD	29.8±4.47		30.57±4.74	

Table 2
Gender distribution
(n=70)

Gender	Group D		Group T	
	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%
Male	6	17.1	10	28.6
Female	29	82.9	25	71.4
Total	35	100	35	100

Table 3
Comparison of mean shivering duration
(n=70)

Duration	Group D		Group T	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
	3.74	1.06	4.97	1.22

P value: 0.0001

Table 4
Comparison of grade of shivering
(n=70)

Grade of shivering	Group D		Group T	
	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%
Grade 0	-	-	-	-
Grade 1	18	51.4	3	8.6
Grade 2	14	40	23	65.7
Grade 3	3	8.6	9	25.7
Grade 4	-	-	-	-
Total	36	100	35	100

Table 5
Comparison of recurrence of shivering
(n=70)

Recurrence of shivering	Group D		Group T	
	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%
Yes	6	17.1	9	25.7
No	29	82.9	26	74.3
Total	35	100	35	100

Table 6
Comparison of mean shivering duration by age
(n=70)

Age (in years)	Group D		Group T		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
18-30	3.83	1.167	5.18	1.26	0.0001
31-40	3.55	0.82	4.62	1.12	0.016

Table 7
Comparison of mean shivering duration by gender
(n=70)

Gender	Group D		Group T		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	3.50	0.84	5.20	1.03	0.004
Female	3.79	1.11	4.88	1.30	0.002

Table 8
Comparison of mean shivering duration by grade of shivering
(n=70)

Grade of shivering	Group D		Group T		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	3.83	1.04	5.67	0.58	0.009
2	3.29	0.83	4.87	1.29	0.000
3	5.33	0.58	5.00	1.22	0.666

Table 9
Comparison of mean shivering duration by recurrence of shivering
(n=70)

Recurrence of shivering	Group D		Group T		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Yes	4.83	1.17	4.67	1.00	0.772
No	3.52	0.91	5.08	1.29	0.000

DISCUSSION

Shivering is an involuntary, repeated muscular movement after anaesthesia. Shivering occurs in 40-50% of studies. It can triple oxygen and CO₂ consumption. Shivering increases intraocular and intracranial pressure and can delay wound healing and post-anaesthesia care discharge. Pharmacological and nonpharmacological techniques treat shivering. Tramadol is a popular medicine for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering. It causes nausea, vomiting, dizziness, etc., which is uncomfortable for the patient. Dexmedetomidine is a 2-adrenoceptor agonist. It's a sedative and reduces shivering threshold. Few studies have studied dexmedetomidine's anti-shivering potential and found it to be efficacious, safe, and hemodynamically stable.

Although, both these drugs are used for management of post-spinal anaesthesia shivering but which of these drugs is superior in efficacy than the other is still debatable due to controversial results of previous studies. Moreover, sub-optimal conditions of temperature control in operating rooms and aberrant drug supply at my study setting makes it imperative to compare the efficacy of dexmedetomidine versus tramadol in management of post-spinal anaesthesia shivering.

In our study, mean age in Group D was 29.8 ± 4.47 and in Group T was 30.57 ± 4.74 , 6(17.1%) of Group D and 10(28.6%) of Group T were male, while 29(82.9%) of Group D and 25(71.4%) of Group T were female. Mean shivering duration in Group D was 3.74 ± 1.06 and 4.97 ± 1.22 in Group T, $p=0.0001$. Shivering recurrence was 6.1% in Group D and 25% in Group T.

Comparing dexmedetomidine and tramadol for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering has shown mixed results. A recent meta-analysis compared dexmedetomidine and tramadol for treating shivering after spinal anaesthesia. Dexmedetomidine was significantly superior to tramadol with shorter duration of shivering cessation (mean difference MD = -2.14; 95%CI [2.79, 1.49], $P 0.00001$, $I^2 = 98\%$), lower recurrent rate of shivering⁸. In another trial, dexmedetomidine was more effective than tramadol for treating shivering during spinal anaesthesia in caesarean section patients (3.8 ± 1.12) than tramadol (5.12 ± 1.27).⁹ Sarwer et al. compared dexmedetomidine with tramadol for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering, hemodynamic alterations, and adverse effects. Duration of post-spinal shivering cessation [dexmedetomidine group 6.20 ± 1.21 minutes versus tramadol group 5.87 ± 1.47 minutes; $p = 0.344$] and return of shivering ($p = 0.161$) were not significantly different between the two

medications. 3 of 30 tramadol patients exhibited bradycardia compared to 1 of 30 dexmedetomidine individuals ($p = 0.301$), whereas no patient developed hypotension or respiratory depression.¹⁰

Geeta Mittal and others⁶⁸ evaluated and compare the efficacy, haemodynamic and adverse effects of dexmedetomidine with those of tramadol, when used for control of post-spinal anaesthesia shivering. It was revealed that time taken for cessation of shivering was significantly less with dexmedetomidine when compared to tramadol. Nausea and vomiting was observed only in tramadol group (28% and; 20% respectively). There was not much difference in the sedation profile of both the drugs.

It was concluded that although both drugs are effective, the time taken for cessation of shivering is less with dexmedetomidine when compared to tramadol. Moreover, dexmedetomidine has negligible adverse effects, whereas tramadol is associated with significant nausea and vomiting.

Alpha-2 adrenergic agonists are widely used nowadays in anaesthesia and intensive care settings. Dexmedetomidine is an α_2 adrenoceptor agonist, with antihypertensive, sedative, analgesic, and anti-shivering properties.⁶⁹ The anti-shivering

effects of alpha adrenoceptor agonists are mediated by binding to α_2 receptors that mediate vasoconstriction and the anti-shivering effect. In addition, it has hypothalamic thermoregulatory effects.⁷⁰ Dexmedetomidine comparably reduces the vasoconstriction and shivering thresholds, thus suggesting that it acts on the central thermoregulatory system rather than preventing shivering peripherally.⁷¹

It has been successfully used as an adjunct to local anaesthetics in spinal anaesthesia and peripheral nerve blockade, for the sedation of mechanically ventilated patients in the Intensive Care Unit, as well as supplementation of post-operative analgesia.⁶⁹ The role of dexmedetomidine in the treatment of shivering has been evaluated in a few studies.⁶⁵ It may be a good choice because of its dual effects related 'anti-shivering' and sedation.

With same dose, that is, 0.5 mg/kg of tramadol, the response rate reported by Shukla et al. was 92.5%, by Reddy and Chiruvella as 95.56% and by Tsai and Chu, 87%.⁶³⁻⁶⁴ It was found 100% response rate in our study. Maheshwari et al. reported similar recurrence rate with tramadol as in our study (8%) but the dose used in their study was 1 mg/kg.⁷² The recurrence rate in the study by Shukla et al. was 5%, which is similar to these

results. The incidence of nausea and vomiting with tramadol in our study was 28% and 20%, respectively. The results correspond with that of other studies by Reddy and Chiruvella, Tsai and Chu; Bansal and Jain.^{64,73,74}

However, in the study by Shukla et al⁶³ the incidence of nausea was quite high (77.5%), whereas Wason et al. have reported the incidence of nausea as only 4%.²⁵ These variations could be explained by the peculiar patient characteristics in different studies. Maheshwari et al. have reported a very high incidence of sedation to the extent of 84%, which as mentioned earlier could be due to the higher dose as opposed to 28% sedation in the study.⁷²

The results of our study justified the hypothesis that **"alternate hypothesis is that dexmedetomidine has greater efficacy and lesser side effects (bradycardia, hypotension, respiratory depression) as compared to tramadol for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering"**, however, further multicenter trials are required to validate our results.

CONCLUSION

- We concluded that that dexmedetomidine has greater efficacy and as compared to tramadol for post-spinal anaesthesia shivering

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PROFORMA**COMPARISON OF EFFICACY OF DEXMEDETOMIDINE
VERSUS TRAMADOL FOR POST-SPINAL ANAESTHESIA
SHIVERING**

AGE: _____

SEX: _____

GROUP ASSIGNED

- GROUP D

- GROUP T

SEVERITY OF SHIVERING (GRADE) _____/5

DURATION OF CESSATION OF SHIVERING _____

RECURRENCE OF SHIVERING

(YES___ / NO___)

SIDE EFFECT(s)

- BRADYCARDIA

- HYPOTENSION

- RESPIRATORY DEPRESSION